

ISSN 2181-0000
Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-0000

JOURNAL OF MAMUN SCIENCE

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 2 **2024**

ISSN 2181-0000
Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-0000

«MA'MUN SCIENCE» JURNALI

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ЖУРНАЛ «MAMUN SCIENCE»

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JOURNAL OF «MAMUN SCIENCE»

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 2

TOSHKENT-2024

«MA'MUN SCIENCE» JURNALI

ЖУРНАЛ «МА'МUN SCIENCE» | JOURNAL OF «MAMUN SCIENCE»

№2 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0000-2024-2>

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WHAT IS PRAGMALINGUISTICS IN LINGUISTICS?

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12515413>

ABSTRACT

Some problems of Pragma linguistics highlighted in this article. It is the study of language use from the viewpoint of the language's structural resources. For instance, it may start with the pronoun system of a language, and examine the way in which people choose different available forms to express the range of attitudes and relationships (such as deference and intimacy). It is a medium where we examine how people convey different kinds of meanings with the use of language or how people express a variety of meaning with variety of people. It is the study of mutual world knowledge. In this sense, the various innovations that have taken place around pragmalinguistics, the developed scientific-theoretical views and research results have attracted linguists, and remain one of the most pressing issues.

Keywords: Pragmalinguistics, language, speaker, hearer, context, speech, dialogue, monologue, linguistics.

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TILSHUNOSLIKDA PRAGMALINGVISTIKA NIMA?

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada pragma tilshunosligining ba'zi muammolari yoritilgan. Pragma tilshunoslik bu tilning strukturaviy resurslari nuqtai nazaridan tildan foydalanishni o'rganishdir. Masalan, u tilning olmosh tizimidan boshlanib, odamlarning munosabat va munosabatlar doirasini (masalan, hurmat va yaqinlik kabi) ifodalash uchun turli xil mavjud shakllarni tanlash usulini o'rganishi mumkin. Bu biz odamlarning turli xil ma'nolarni til yordamida qanday etkazishini yoki odamlar turli xil odamlar bilan qanday qilib turli xil ma'nolarni ifodalashlarini o'rganadigan vositadir. Bu o'zaro dunyo bilimlarini o'rganishdir. Shu ma'noda pragmalingvistika atrofida ro'y bergan turli yangiliklar, ishlab chiqilgan ilmiy-nazariy qarashlar, tadqiqot natijalari tilshunos olimlarni o'ziga jalb etib, dolzarb masalalardan biri bo'lib qolmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: Pragmalingvistika, til, so'zlovchi, tinglovchi, kontekst, nutq, dialog, monolog, tilshunoslik.

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ЧТО ТАКОЕ ПРАГМАЛИНГВИСТИКА В ЛИНГВИСТИКЕ?

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье освещены некоторые проблемы прагмалингвистики. Это изучение использования языка с точки зрения структурных ресурсов языка. Например, он может начинаться с системы местоимений языка и исследовать то, как люди выбирают различные доступные формы для выражения различных отношений и отношений (таких как почтительность и близость). Это среда, в которой мы изучаем, как люди передают различные значения с помощью языка или как люди выражают различные значения с помощью разных людей. Это изучение взаимного познания мира. В этом смысле различные новшества, произошедшие вокруг прагмалингвистики, выработанные научно-теоретические взгляды и результаты исследований привлекли лингвистов и остаются одной из самых актуальных проблем.

Ключевые слова: Прагмалингвистика, язык, говорящий, слушающий, контекст, речь, диалог, монолог, лингвистика.

INTRODUCTION.

While the field of pragmatics in its widest sense is constituted of many diverse approaches (without clear-cut boundaries) united by a common functional (social, cultural, cognitive) perspective on language in communication, **pragmalinguistics** (linguistic pragmatics, pragmatic linguistics, internal pragmatics) focuses primarily (though not exclusively) on the study of linguistic phenomena (i.e., code) from the point of view of their usage. As it is impossible to offer an exhaustive definition of pragmatics, it might be easier simply to present a list of the topics studied: deixis, implicature, presupposition, speech acts and aspects of discourse structure. The phenomenon of **deixis** fixes the utterance in the physical and social (**social deixis**, which includes **person deixis** and **attitudinal deixis**) context of its use. Deixis, which may also be used 'self-referentially' to point to itself, is realized by indexical (deictic) expressions, such as personal and possessive pronouns, adverbials, verbal categories of person and tense, but also by politeness and phatic formulae.

MATERIAL AND METHODS.

Pragmalinguistics and Communication are considerable parts of any language. Therefore, plenty of scholars study them. For example, Russian scholars V.V. Vinogradov, A.I. Smidnitski, H.N. Asomova and Uzbek scholars Sh. Rahmatullayev, A.E. Mamatov, B. Yo'ldoshev conducted a research on this sphere of linguistics. Their works and researches play significant role in the development of phraseology. There are still unexplained problems with the nature of the pragmalinguistics and communication and their study and resolution suggests a new approach to modern linguistic approach.

In world linguistics, a number of fundamental studies are being conducted to identify the social factors influencing the development the presentation of dialogic speech as a type of speech activity that has a communicative and functional-pragmatic orientation. This made it possible to prove that, like any other activity, speech activity is regulated by certain rules. The dissertation systematizes and describes ten main extralinguistic principles of English dialogical speech constitution, and an attempt is made to analyze the interaction of the selected principles, the degree of their significance for organizing a conflict-free dialogue, as well as the features of speech means of their expression. This study identifies and systematizes in a new way the factors that contribute to the actualization of the personal characteristics of communicants in the dialogue, and analyzes

the influence of the communicative situation on the actualization of the personal properties of the participants in the dialogue and their choice of speech means of influencing the interlocutor.

The complex use of modern research methods, including as the main ones: the hypothetical-deductive method, the method of semantic-syntactic description of statements of various types, the method of contextual analysis, as well as elements of propositional, intentional and actor-speech analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.

While the field of pragmatics in its widest sense is constituted of many diverse approaches (without clear-cut boundaries) united by a common functional (social, cultural, cognitive) perspective on language in communication, **pragmalinguistics** (linguistic pragmatics, pragmatic linguistics, internal pragmatics) focuses primarily (though not exclusively) on the study of linguistic phenomena (i.e., code) from the point of view of their usage. As it is impossible to offer an exhaustive definition of pragmatics, it might be easier simply to present a list of the topics studied: deixis, implicature, presupposition, speech acts and aspects of discourse structure. The phenomenon of **deixis** fixes the utterance in the physical and social (**social deixis**, which includes **person deixis** and **attitudinal deixis**) context of its use. Deixis, which may also be used 'self-referentially' to point to itself, is realized by indexical (deictic) expressions, such as personal and possessive pronouns, adverbials, verbal categories of person and tense, but also by politeness and phatic formulae.

Presupposition represents the amount of information assumed to be known by participants (background knowledge, common ground) and has direct impact on how much is explicitly said and how much remains implicit. Since it is normally not necessary, let alone possible, to be fully explicit, a certain level of balance is strived for by the participants who take into consideration various factors; for example, the medium of writing tends to be more explicit as participants do not share the time and space, often an unknown (general) addressee is projected with whom the amount of the shared knowledge can only be estimated. The theory of **speech acts** concerns the language user's intention to attain certain communicative goals by performing acts through the use of language. From the stylistic perspective, Austin's three types of speech act (locutionary, illocutionary, perlocutionary) are of special relevance, since it is esp. the variety of possible illocutions (i.e., uses which language can be put to) which offers innumerable choices. The types of speech acts as proposed by Searle (assertives, directives, commissives, expressives, declarations) are (loosely) associated with certain linguistic categories (utterance types). Of special significance is the relation between locution (locutionary meaning or propositional meaning) and illocution (illocutionary meaning, or illocutionary force) as this is not always of the one-to-one type: one locution may have more than one illocution. For example, The dinner is ready may be announcement, invitation, threat, command, etc. Conventionally, this utterance will be interpreted as an invitation to join the table rather than an announcement, hence an example of an **indirect speech act**. The use of indirect illocutions in preference to direct ones is often driven by the need to protect partner's face (i.e., politeness concerns, esp. in requests and refusals). Similarly, the strategy of **hedging** is used to play down the illocutionary force of utterances (while demonstrating the metapragmatic awareness by explicitly referring to CP maxims) while employing a variety of linguistic manifestations (hedges, mitigators: sort of, kind of, in a sense, I hate to say this, partial agreement before presenting disagreement: Yes, but..., using performatives in business correspondence: *We are sorry to have to tell you...*, etc.). **Weasel words** are used to temper the straightforwardness of a statement making thus one's views equivocal (e.g., *borrow* instead of *steal*, *crisis* instead of *war*); in the pejorative sense they help avoid responsibility for one's claim (e.g., The results of the experiment appear to be in direct contradiction with the stated hypotheses). Explicit use of performative verbs may cause a shift in formality level and create an atmosphere of authoritative claim (*Sit down, I beg you*).

What is implied can be, and often is, 'strategically manipulated' with, if not for outright lying, then certainly for attaining our goals in mundane conversational encounters. The

conversational implicature was proposed as a rational model guiding conversational interaction. Better known as the **Cooperative Principle** (CP), it includes four conversational maxims: quantity, quality, relation, manner. Although presupposed to be adhered to by the participants, the maxims are often deliberately flouted, e.g., in phatic or small talk (quantity), 'white lies' (quality), humour, irony, teasing, banter, puns (manner), topic shift, seemingly irrelevant remarks whose relevance is implied and may only be disclosed by inference (relation). Some **tropes** (figures of speech) are built on the breach of CP: hyperbole (exaggeration: to wait an eternity), litotes (understatement, esp. that in which an affirmative is expressed by the negative of its contrary: *not bad at all*), tautology (repetition: *War is war, and there will be losers*), paraphrase, euphemism, metaphor and esp. irony (conveys a meaning that is the opposite of its literal meaning: *How nice! said after someone's I failed another exam*). The maxims of CP are successfully applied in literary stylistics, for example in order to draw 'pragmatic portraits' of fictional heroes.

As can be seen from the previous examples, the maxims of CP are often conventionally suppressed in favor of maintaining the 'social equilibrium' which may be just as important as the cooperation itself (it may even be more important as in white lies, i.e., minor, polite, or harmless lies). The need not to cause any damage to and to uphold each others' **face** (e.g., not criticizing the quality of service or food in the restaurant directly) is the central problem of the theories of **politeness**. G. Leech proposes the six maxims of **Politeness Principle** (PP) as a way of complementing the CP and thus 'rescuing' it from serious 'trouble' (i.e., accounting for the situations when a strict adherence to CP would be unacceptable): tact, generosity, approbation, modesty, agreement, sympathy.

The tact maxim regulates the operation of the directive speech acts (which are marked with highest face-threatening potential) and addresses the dominant type of politeness which, with regard to the addressee, can be 'measured' on the **cost-benefit scale**: the more costly an action, the less polite it is, and, conversely, the more beneficial it is to the addressee, the more polite it is. This helps explain why, for example, imperative mood is not necessarily associated with impoliteness: *Bring me some water* vs. *Have another drink*. Next, **optionality scale** is used to rank options according to the degree of choice offered to the addressee - the degree of politeness matches the degree of indirectness (tentativeness), and, vice versa, increased directness results in greater impoliteness (e.g., *Lend me your car* vs. *Do you think you could possibly lend me your car?*). It appears that while imperatives offer little option of whether or not to comply with the action requested (*Give me some change*), questions (*Have you got a quarter, by any chance?*), hypothetical formulations (*Could I borrow some money?*), and ones using negatives (*You couldn't lend me a dollar, could you?*) provide greater freedom to deny that request. Of course, politeness formulae (please) can always be added to give extra politeness. We should also differentiate between **absolute** and **relative** politeness; in the absolute sense, *Lend me your car* is less polite than *I hope you don't mind my asking, but I wonder if it might be at all possible for you to lend me your car*. However, in some situations, the former request could be over-polite (among family members) and the latter one impolite (as an ironic remark). The aspects of **face** (i.e., a self-image or impression of oneself presented publicly) are studied within the theories of politeness among which a prominent place is held by Brown and Levinson's model. They claim that in any social interaction participants devote much of their time to **face-work**, i.e., strategies attending to aspects of their own face (viz. attempting not to lose it) as well as of other's face (not threatening it by performing a **face-threatening act**, such as requesting, denying an invitation, rejecting an offer, or an other-repair).

CONCLUSIONS.

There are two types of face: **negative face** (the freedom of individual action, a desire to be unimpeded) and **positive face** (the need to be treated as equal, a desire for approval). Corresponding to these are the two types of strategies: **negative politeness strategies** (strategies of independence, also called deference politeness strategies) attend to hearer's negative face and include the use of expressions indicative of indirectness, tentativeness, impersonality, social distance: mitigators

(*Sorry to interrupt, but...*), euphemisms and politically correct language; **positive politeness strategies** (strategies of involvement, also called solidarity politeness strategies) attempt to save hearer's positive face by emphasizing closeness, intimacy, commonality and rapport. The key factors determining the choice of appropriate strategy are, a) the relationship between participants, i.e., their relative power (social status) difference, and their social distance (the degree of closeness), and, b) the degree of imposition/urgency (K.C.C.Kong adds a mutual expectation of relationship continuity as another factor). Depending on the degree of threat upon the addressee's face, five **politeness strategies** can be identified:

- a) **bald-on-record** (open, direct) in case the risk of loss of face is minimum (*Fetch me some water*);
- b) **solidarity politeness** which addresses the common ground (*I know I can always rely on you, could you lend me your typewriter?*);
- c) **deference politeness**, when the imposition is serious (*I hate to impose on you but I wonder if you could possibly let me use your computer?*);
- d) **off record**, an imposition is so great that it must be proffered indirectly (*I'm all out of money - this may be a source of ambiguity since it is up to the hearer to interpret this as a request*);
- e) **not saying anything**, since the threat of loss of face is too great.

From the viewpoint of language users' intentions, their choices from the total pool of resources and the effects upon other participants, the legitimacy of the pragmatic perspective for stylistically-oriented study can hardly be denied.

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ISSN 2181-9696

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9696

«MA'MUN SCIENCE» JURNALI

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VOLUME 2, ISSUE 2

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